

ISSUES OF ENSURING A SAME DROP OF TAX REVENUES ON THE BASIS OF ENSURING MACROECONOMIC STABILITY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. Ensuring uniform collection of tax revenues in Uzbekistan is the main issue expected from tax reform, as well as a priority issue of tax policy. Of course, this is influenced by many factors and various means are used to ensure this. At the same time, there are certain scientific and practical problems in this regard. This article focuses on these aspects.

Key words: tax revenues, budget, state budget, macroeconomic stability, tax revenues, tax reform, economic growth, tax policy, taxation, tax administration, tax benefits, honest taxpayer, tax evasion, tax strategy, tax policy tactics.

The goal of any country's tax reform and tax policy is to ensure that mandatory payments to the state's target and target funds are made at the same time. The provision of social services financed from the state budget depends on the timely arrival of tax and non-tax revenues, on the other hand, the timely arrival of tax revenues depends on many other factors.

Economic growth in our republic is achieved due to consistent continuation of structural reforms, as well as ensuring macroeconomic stability through mutually balanced fiscal and monetary policy. According to forecasts, the economy of Uzbekistan is expected to grow by 5.6-5.8 percent in 2023-2024, and up to 6.2 and 6.4 percent in 2025-2026, respectively. In this, it was forecasted based on the goal of reaching 4,000 US dollars per capita GDP by 2030. For this purpose, in order to ensure stable growth of Uzbekistan despite the economic and political uncertainties observed in the world in the following years: - development of human capital; - energy resources market reform; - acceleration of privatization and transformation of enterprises; - implementation of measures related to the rational use of natural resources, especially water resources; - measures are being taken to expand the use of public-private partnership projects in the development of social and industrial infrastructure.

According to the October 2023 report of the International Monetary Fund, economic growth is expected to slow down next year as a result of the continuation

of strict monetary policy in the global economy in the context of high global inflation, as well as the implementation of fiscal consolidation in order to reduce the burden of public debt in a number of countries. In particular, according to this report, the world economy slowed down from 3.0 percent in 2023, to 2.9 percent in 2024, and the economy of developed countries slowed down from 1.5 percent to 1.4 percent, respectively. Although the economic growth rate of 4% in the current year has been preserved in the economies of developing countries, the economy of the main trade partners of our country, including Russia, will increase from 2.2% in 2023 to 1.1% in 2024, China from 5.0% to 4.2%, Turkey's economy from 4.0 from 3.0% to 3.0% and Kazakhstan from 4.6% to 4.2%.

1-table.

of the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank in 2023-2024 countries in the region and major trade partners economic growth forecasts ¹for in percent

Countries	2023 year	2024 year	2023 year	2024 year
Jahan economy	3.0	2.9	2.5	2.1
Russia	2.2	1.1	1.6	1.3
China	5.0	4.2	5.1	4.6
Turkey	4.0	3.0	4.2	3.1
Kazakhstan	4.6	4.2	4.5	4.3
Kyrgyzstan	3.4	4.3	3.5	4.0
Tajikistan	6.5	5.0	6.5	5.0
Azerbaijan	2.5	2.5	1.5	2.4
Georgia	6.2	4.8	5.9	4.8

2023 of the year international finance organizations by prepared according to the information of Uzbekistan economic growth i 2023 in gross internal product growth 5, 6 percentage around and 2024 per year go this indicator 5.5-5.6 percentages around be Last 7 in global in economics being observed complicated to the situation regardless the country development strategies the economy to liberalize directed reforms done being increased and programs aimed at the development of networks, sectors and regions done increase as a result 2023 in too stable economic growth to the pace (5.6-5.8 percent) has been achieved.

Table 2 .

Main macroeconomic indicators analysis and predictions²

¹ International Monetary Fund and the world of the bank in October 2023 reports .

² Economy and finance compiled by the author based on the information of the ministry .

Indicators	2022 year	2023 year	2024 year	2025 year	2026 year
Gross internal product , <i>billion soum</i>	888 342	1 061 184	1 301 759	1 540 547	1 725 969
Gross internal product growthpace , <i>in percent</i>	5.7	5.6-5.8	5.6-5.8	6.2	6.4
Population soul per head gross internal product volume , <i>US dollar</i>	2 254	2 449	2 698	2 950	3 055
Industry , billion amount	551 051	647 932	782 710	972 107	1 174 017
<i>growth pace , in percent</i>	5.2	5.5-6	6.0	7.6	7.5
construction , <i>billion soum</i>	130 767	157 493	188 342	223 506	261 236
<i>growth pace , in percent</i>	6.6	6.0	6.3	7.2	7.3
Village , forest and fisheries , <i>billion soum growth pace , in percent</i>	364 523	428 289	488 397	547 251	611 166
Market services , <i>billion soum</i>	3.6	3.7	4.0	4.1	4.1
<i>growth pace , in percent</i>	357 555	450 437	580 532	711 011	896 775
<i>growth pace , in percent</i>	15.9	13.0	14.9	14.0	14.9

It can be seen from the above tables that stable development and macroeconomic stability in the national economy of Uzbekistan are the financial basis for the steady flow of tax revenues to the state budget.

As a result of these macroeconomic factors, the State budget revenues in 2021 will be 164.7 trillion. amounted to 31.7 trillion soums compared to 2020. increased by 23.9% to 202 trillion soums in 2022 (22.7% of GDP) and increased by 37.2 trillion soums or 22.6% compared to 2021, and in 2023, the State budget income forecast indicators compared to 100.4%, the actual execution was 233.6 trillion soums, and this of the year to income relatively 31.7 billion to soum or 15.7 means more than percent. In turn, through taxes collected by the Tax Committee in 2023 167.1 trillion soums of revenue were generated, according to the Customs Committee 56.7 trillion soums were charged to the budget. Forecast of consolidated budget parameters for 2024 and 2025–2026 years for goals the world in the economy continue doing uncertainties, oil, gas, mineral fertilizers and food in the world market in prices of vibrations internal to the market of influence continue will be affected. Uzbekistan Republic consolidated of the budget 2024 of the year income 375.0 trillion soum and expenses 427.5 trillion soum, shortage 52.5 trillion soums or 4.0 per gross product The amount of the consolidated budget deficit in 2024 is determined as a

percentage determination of uncertainties in the world economy and geopolitical situation to soften the impact on the economy of our country, it needs social protection to further strengthen the state support of the population payment ability fall down of leaving prevention get events addition allocation of funds, additional benefits and preferences for entrepreneurs to be given as a result budget of losses come exit with explained.

In our opinion, in order to increase the impact of tax revenues through macroeconomic stability in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to continue reforms in the following directions:

First direction – economy network and fields stable development for necessary conditions creation, which leads to the emergence of an additional tax base;

second direction – 2024 in industry in the network work releasesize 6 percent (783 trillion soum) increase for started in previous years 319 ta big projects own in time to work to drop demand reaches;

the third direction is productivity in agriculture and water management continue reforms aimed at increasing and problems in the field by implementing measures to eliminate the potential of the regions taking into account the agricultural growth rate of 4 percent in 2024 (488 trillion sum), next in years 4.5-5 percentage to the level deliver according to measuresdone increase demand is done;

the fourth direction - services market development through Market services growth in 2024 at the level of 14.9 percent (574 trillion soums) it will be necessary to provide;

the fifth direction – bank in the system financial stability strengthening and their State to the activity intervention will need to be limited;

sixth direction – budget shortage 2024 in gross internal not to exceed 4 percent for the product and 3 percent in future yearsaccording to budget it is necessary to strengthen discipline and strengthen cooperation with the International Monetary Fund, the World Bank, and the Asian Development Bank.

We believe that if we continue the reforms in the 6 areas listed above, macroeconomic stability in Uzbekistan will increase further, leading to the creation of additional tax bases, and tax revenues will be provided to the state budget.

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